

Increasing inoculation effectiveness in European soybean with indigenous *Bradyrhizobium* strains

Problem

Drought stress in spring inhibits the activity of introduced rhizobia through inoculation in central Europe. Reduced nodulation affects biological nitrogen fixation and soybean grain and protein yield.

Solution

Identify indigenous *Bradyrhizobium* for inoculating soybean seeds to enhance nodulation.

Benefits

Higher soybean grain yield and protein content with indigenous *Bradyrhizobium* formulations.

In Brandenburg, highest grain yield was achieved in soybeans inoculated with strain GMF14 & GMM36, isolated from an arable field in northeast Germany (Fig 1a). There was an up to 5% increase in protein yield with the strain GMF14 inoculation compared to the commercial USDA110 (Fig 1b).

Applicability box

Theme

Soybean production in non-traditional climates

Keywords

Nitrogen fixation, nodulation, soybean grain yield & grain protein

Context

Central Europe

Application time

Spring (sowing)

Required time

Growing season of soybean

Period of impact

During growing season and subsequent crop

Equipment

Not necessary

Best in

Soybean production

Fig 1. Mean effect of *Bradyrhizobia* strain on (a) soybean grain yield and (b) protein yield averaged across three years of field trials in rainfed conditions in Müncheberg, Germany.

Practical Advice

- Isolation and culturing of soybean rhizobia require microbiological expertise typically available in specialized commercial or scientific institutions.

- Isolated and cultured inoculum with a carrier can be used to inoculate seeds at the farm.
- For one kilogram of soybean seeds, mix 65 ml of pure *Bradyrhizobium* culture (2×10^8 cells ml⁻¹) with 10 g peat or biochar carrier.
- Volume of *Bradyrhizobium* culture should be adjusted based on seed size and weight.
- Inoculate seeds just before sowing.
- To maintain seed viability, it is recommended to coat seeds with inoculum-carrier paste rather than soaking them in liquid *Bradyrhizobium* culture.

No inoculation

Inoculation with indigenous strain

Established soybean plants at the ZALF experimental station, Brandenburg, Germany

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About this practice abstract

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LegumES – Valorization of ecosystem services provided by legume crops - aims to share, showcase, co-develop, and implement the knowledge, key agronomic practices, methodologies, and tools which will allow optimized legume-based systems, and valorization of the ES benefits provided.

Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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